

The Human Oversight approaches at the forefront of responsible and trustworthy AI, from data-centric adaptive AI-Ops pipelines to Multi-Agent Systems

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Abstract — The paper focuses on human oversight mechanisms in Artificial Intelligence (AI) systems and their pipelines, with particular attention to Human-in-the-Loop (HITL) and Human-on-the-Loop (HOTL) approaches. It explores their main advantages and challenges over fully autonomous systems, from a technical, legal and ethical perspective. The study discusses how the adoption of human judgment and feedback can address critical gaps in accuracy, accountability, fairness, transparency, and trust, especially when combined with explainable AI (XAI) techniques. However, such a human oversight paradigm can also raise issues, including scalability constraints, human error, cognitive load and fatigue, as well as biases in training data, privacy risks, “rubber stamping”, or even legal liability. These concepts, advantages and challenges are first analysed through a literature review, and then further explored through the AI-DAPT project, highlighting the implementation of techniques and measures for embedding human oversight in adaptive AI-Ops pipelines. The paper further examines the AI-DAPT healthcare domain and its pilot case and reflects on technical, ethical, and legal insights, including the future role of human oversight in the context of Agentic AI.

Keywords — *Human-in-the-Loop, Human-on-the-Loop, Human-in-Command, accuracy, decision-making, model performance, XAI, adaptive AI-Ops pipeline, biases, ethics, trustworthy AI.*

I. INTRODUCTION

The increasing development and adoption of assorted algorithmic decision-making systems are coupled with the need to create interactive dimensions where people and technology jointly collaborate towards a shared endeavor and humans are kept in the loop of the decision-making at stake, maintaining human agency and accountability, providing legal safeguards, or performing quality control. The introduction of such interactive dimension results in various forms of hybrid decision-making, where algorithmic and human agents collaborate, holding great promise for solving complex problems in several domains [1]. The human oversight, combining human judgment with machine

intelligence, is considered an effective way to address the issues and challenges, such as those of transparency, bias, and systemic risks, relating to automation. Therefore, with the increasing adoption of AI systems, organisations are increasingly leveraging human-oversight-driven workflows to manage risks, ensure compliance, and address ethical concerns, with the anticipated gains in accuracy, user satisfaction, and risk reduction across critical AI applications, as suggested by the literature. However, in operational AI systems, human oversight cannot be treated only as a broad ethical principle. Its effectiveness depends on how human roles are positioned within the AI lifecycle, including data preparation, model validation, deployment, monitoring, and decision support.

This paper approaches human oversight not as a generic safeguard, but as a design concern that must be connected to concrete AI pipeline functions. Considering the growing relevance of the topic for ethically-driven and trustworthy AI, as well as legal provisions demanding it in high-risk AI systems [2], the paper analyses the opportunities and challenges associated with its adoption, with particular attention to Human-in-the-Loop (HITL) and Human-on-the-Loop (HOTL) approaches. The discussion is grounded in the advancements proposed by the AI DAPT project [3], which directly addresses the friction between autonomous efficiency and meaningful human oversight by introducing a data-centric paradigm that fuses end-to-end automation with a human oversight approach across the AI-Ops lifecycle. The high-level vision, achievements, as well technological-driven and ethics-focused insights resulting by the AI-DAPT action are complemented by a deep dive into its healthcare case study and by the investigation of the expected evolving role, emerging trends and future direction of the human oversight approaches in relation to the technological advances, which are moving towards the Agentic AI.

II. CONCEPT AND STATE OF THE ART OF HUMAN OVERSIGHT FROM THE ETHICS AND TECHNICAL PERSPECTIVE

A. Human oversight concepts and definitions

Human oversight refers to mechanisms through which human actors supervise, intervene, or retain authority over AI systems during their development, deployment, or operational phases. It can be embedded at multiple stages of the AI lifecycle, including data annotation, model training, validation, decision approval, monitoring of outputs, and system governance. The goal is not merely to correct errors but also to ensure that AI systems remain aligned with human values, legal requirements, and domain-specific expertise. In this context, human oversight is increasingly recognized as a critical design principle for trustworthy AI systems, particularly in domains where automated decisions may significantly affect individuals or society [4] [5] [6].

One of the most widely discussed paradigms is **Human-in-the-Loop (HITL)**. In HITL systems, human actors directly participate in the operational workflow of an AI system, typically providing input that influences the model’s training, evaluation, or decision outputs. This participation often takes the form of data labeling, annotation, providing system inputs, or correction of outputs [7] [8]. HITL approaches are commonly used in supervised learning environments and reinforcement learning with human feedback (RLHF), where human expertise contributes to improving model accuracy, transparency, and trustworthiness [9] [10]. HITL mechanisms enable AI systems to benefit from domain knowledge that may not be easily captured through automated learning processes. This is particularly relevant in complex domains such as healthcare, where contextual interpretation and professional expertise play a crucial role.

A related but distinct paradigm is **Human-on-the-Loop (HOTL)**. In HOTL systems, human actors supervise the operation of an AI system without being directly involved in individual decisions. Instead of actively participating in the workflow, humans monitor system behavior and retain the ability to intervene or override decisions when necessary. This supervisory model is often adopted in systems where automation performs most operational tasks, but human oversight remains available to ensure safety, reliability, and accountability [11]. The HOTL paradigm seeks to balance efficiency and oversight, requiring robust monitoring mechanisms and effective alert systems to enable human supervisors to identify anomalies or potential risks.

Beyond these operational paradigms, the concept of **Human-in-Command (HIC)** represents a broader governance perspective on human oversight. Unlike HITL and HOTL, which focus primarily on operational involvement in technical workflows, HIC emphasizes the role of humans in maintaining ultimate authority and responsibility over AI systems. Under the HIC approach, human actors retain decision-making authority regarding the objectives, deployment conditions, and acceptable uses of AI technologies. This model is particularly relevant in regulatory and ethical discussions, where the emphasis lies on ensuring that AI systems remain under meaningful human control and that accountability can be clearly assigned [12]. Therefore, HIC operates at a higher level of system governance, complementing the operational models of HITL and HOTL, and encompassing activities such as setting operational constraints, defining risk thresholds, establishing oversight procedures, and determining when automated

recommendations should be accepted, rejected, or further evaluated.

These **approaches** are **not mutually exclusive**. Rather, they may coexist within the same AI system at different stages of the lifecycle. For example, a system may employ HITL during training, HOTL during operational monitoring, and HIC at the governance level to define policies and accountability structures [13]. Each model implies a different operational arrangement between humans and AI components. HITL introduces human input as part of the execution of a specific task or workflow step. HOTL preserves a higher level of automation but requires mechanisms for monitoring, alerting, and intervention. HIC establishes broader human authority over the objectives, constraints, and acceptable uses of the system. Clarifying these differences helps avoid treating human oversight as a single generic requirement and supports a more precise discussion of its role in trustworthy AI pipelines (see table 1).

Oversight model	Human role	AI Pipeline implication
HITL	Direct participation in a task or decision	The workflow may depend on human input before continuing
HOTL	Supervision of automated behaviour	The workflow continues automatically but requires monitoring and intervention mechanisms
HIC	Governance and authority over the system	Humans define objectives, limits, responsibilities, and acceptable uses

Table 1 Oversight models

B. Previous work

Existing work on human oversight can be grouped into three complementary perspectives. The first concerns interactive AI and machine learning approaches, where human input is used to guide training, validation, correction, or decision-making. The second concerns supervisory control approaches, where humans monitor autonomous or semi-autonomous systems and intervene when necessary. The third concerns AI pipelines and MLOps infrastructure, where oversight is supported by traceability, monitoring, auditability, validation gates, and lifecycle management. This categorisation helps clarify how different strands of work contribute to the operationalisation of human oversight.

Early technical implementations of human oversight in AI systems emerged from the **interactive machine learning (IML) and active learning literature**, where human experts are integrated into the model training loop. Systems such as interactive machine learning platforms and active learning pipelines [14] allowed models to query human annotators for informative samples during training, thereby improving data quality and model performance. More recently, the **Reinforced Learning from Human Feedback (RLHF)** has operationalized HITL at scale, particularly in large language models, where human evaluators provide preference signals to guide policy optimization [15]. These implementations demonstrate that human input can improve robustness and

alignment of AI systems, although they often rely on annotation processes and substantial expert involvement, introducing challenges related to scalability, cost, and operational efficiency that may slow down decision-making processes and increase cognitive load for human operators at large scale.

Parallel work has explored supervisory control architectures aligned with the HOTL paradigm. In robotics and autonomous systems, supervisory control models allow automated systems to operate autonomously while human operators monitor system behavior and intervene when necessary. Nahavandi, for example, describes trusted autonomy frameworks in which humans supervise autonomous robotic systems and retain override authority to ensure safety and reliability. Similar supervisory architectures have also been explored in human-automation interaction research, where monitoring dashboards and alert mechanisms enable operators to detect anomalies in semi-autonomous systems [16]. HOTL systems may face limitations related to the phenomenon of “automation bias,” where human operators may become overly reliant on automated recommendations, potentially leading to passive oversight or “rubber-stamping” of AI-generated outputs [17].

Platforms such as **Kubeflow Pipelines** [18] or **AirFlow** [19] enable practitioners to design multi-step machine-learning pipelines that organize stages of the ML lifecycle, including data preparation, model training, validation, and deployment, within reproducible workflows. Airflow is particularly relevant in this context because it provides a mature orchestration model based on directed acyclic graphs, making it suitable for coordinating complex data and AI workflows. However, its adoption also introduces barriers for users who are not familiar with its workflow definition model, since pipeline nodes and dependencies typically need to be specified programmatically. From the perspective of human oversight, this creates a gap between the orchestration capabilities provided by Airflow and the need for more accessible mechanisms through which domain experts can understand, configure, validate, or supervise pipeline execution. Extensions of pipeline-based environments have introduced governance-oriented mechanisms such as artifact tracking, provenance management, and compliance checks that improve traceability and auditability of ML workflow [20] [21] [22]. At a broader level, **MLOps architectures** integrate dataset validation, model evaluation, experiment tracking, and monitoring capabilities that support continuous supervision of deployed model [23]. These mechanisms allow practitioners to monitor system behavior, detect anomalies such as performance degradation or data drift, and maintain visibility over model evolution across the lifecycle. Such developments illustrate a broader shift toward data-centric and lifecycle-oriented AI development, where human expertise contributes not only to model training but also to data governance, validation, and operational monitoring. Consequently, human oversight is increasingly implemented as an architectural component of AI pipelines, embedded in workflow orchestration and monitoring infrastructures rather than as isolated HITL or HOTL interventions [24].

C. Opportunities and Challenges of the Human Oversight approaches and the underlying ethical implications

Ethical implications of HITL and HOTL do not arise only from the presence or absence of human actors, but from the

way human involvement is embedded into AI pipeline execution, monitoring, intervention, and accountability mechanisms. Therefore, this section focuses on the conditions under which human oversight becomes meaningful, rather than assuming that the mere inclusion of a human actor is sufficient to ensure ethical or trustworthy AI.

The emergent HITL and HOTL paradigms provide several opportunities and **benefits** [25]. Such paradigms rely on human expertise, feedback and judgment to augment and improve the accuracy, generalization and trustworthiness of the algorithm, enabling domain experts to provide their knowledge on the model. The human involvement allows enhanced learning and model improvement, and, more in general, the enhancement of ML decision-making capability, besides contributing to ensure that the AI outputs align with ethical and social values of society and legal standards.

The human presence ensures that the decisions or recommendations made by the AI system, which cannot by itself evaluate the broader ethical and social/moral implications of its outputs, are consistent with such values. Such an alignment, in turn, contributes to increase the **users’ acceptance and trust** and the consequent adoption of the AI system itself. The human judgment is also useful to mitigate the **bias**, for instance in case of identification and correction of biases inherent to AI systems designed by humans based on historical data perpetuating inequalities, as well as to handle complex tasks and, more in general, to address **concerns about the fairness, accountability, and transparency** of AI systems. The human oversights, operating in synergy with XAI, mitigates the risks of unpredictable decisions made by the AI system by enabling real-time human intervention, preventing unintended harmful actions. However, these benefits depend on the quality, timing, and usability of the human intervention.

Further advantages of the HITL and HOTL approaches include the valorization of human intuition, **contextual understanding**, and the human ability to manage **exceptions**, ethical dilemmas, and ambiguous contexts [4]. Thanks to such approaches, the user can tailor the system to their own preferences and daily routines, as well as modify its functionality to suit their own context and evolving expectations towards the system, thereby increasing the perceived utility of the system itself, the sense of self-efficacy, user satisfaction and engagement, potentially **preventing future disengagement** and resulting in a more user-centric system [26].

Nevertheless, the human oversight presents also a number of methodological, technical, and ethical **challenges**. They concern not only the cost of involving humans, but also whether human intervention remains meaningful under real operational constraints and include, first of all, the **scalability issues**, due to the time and resources required to integrate the human feedback into the AI workflow, which might slow down the decision-making process. Such a challenge is particularly relevant as the amount of data increases, making it difficult for humans to provide input at the same rate and creating bottlenecks in the learning process. Furthermore, **costs** may also increase since oversight requires highly skilled experts or specialized training [27].

A second set of challenges relates to **human factors**, including **decision fatigue** and cognitive overload due to the excessive reliance on human oversight, which can negatively

impact the effectiveness of the human component. Both HITL and HOTL require humans to understand the AI system limitations, maintain vigilance, and make quick decisions under time and resource constraints. In some situations, the **well-being** of the human expert is underestimated. Human experts may struggle to exercise real autonomy and to assess the lawfulness, proportionality, accuracy and quality of AI-generated decisions or recommendations (and potentially the underlying data). They may also face difficulties in interpreting complex legal requirements while performing contextual analysis and domain-specific judgement [28]. In such conditions, oversight may become less effective and may negatively affect the well-being of the human expert, and as a consequence of cognitive overload, but also for misjudgment, lack of knowledge, or misinterpretation of data, there is also the risk of **human error**.

These considerations can be linked to the **liability allocation** challenge of the human oversight approaches. The liability frameworks surrounding the HITL, HOTL and HIC approaches remain ambiguous and there are unresolved tensions on liability allocation. For instance, in case of adverse outcomes of the AI system, it is discussed whether responsibility resides with the operators or clinicians who accept AI recommendations and it is unclear who is responsible in case of overriding a correct AI recommendation, which leads to adverse outcomes [29]. This shows that meaningful oversight requires clear documentation of intervention points, decision rationales, and the conditions under which human approval, rejection, or override is expected.

A further criticism of the human oversight approaches concerns their potential to act as a "moral crumple zone", where humans provide the appearance of oversight (which allows manufacturers to transfer blame for AI errors to the human operator), thought in practice, it is not possible for them to keep up with the machine's speed or they have too little information to make informed decisions. In such cases, oversight becomes symbolic rather than meaningful.

Besides human error, it is also possible the intentional misuse of the human involvement, in case of malicious individuals who train models that serve their purpose, with possible consequent damages to the society [30]. In addition, the **subjectivity of human input** and the lack of a clear ground truth should be considered, since humans can have different opinions and interpretations of the same data. This might lead to inconsistencies in the validation process and affect the reliability of the feedback used to guide the AI system. In some cases, such inconsistencies may also reproduce or amplify **bias** with consequences for fairness and **data quality** [31].

HITL systems can also raise **data privacy** concerns and pose risks to the protection of personal information, such as medical records and financial information, when human annotators or validators have access to sensitive data. To tackle this concern, several approaches and measures can be adopted, such as relying on synthetic data, anonymization, access control, or techniques such as differential privacy. However, these measures may themselves introduce further challenges [32].

In addition, besides the acknowledged importance of the XAI for an effective human oversight, it is also important that the AI system is accessible to non-experts, adopting **user-**

friendly interfaces that allow humans to effectively guide, correct, and improve AI outputs. An intuitive design prevents the risk that the human becomes a bottleneck, slows down the system processing, or increases errors. In HOTL settings, it is also key to keep humans engaged, aware of the system state, and in the right mental model to intervene when needed, even when not actively involved. These considerations show that the ethical implications of human oversight are inseparable from technical design choices concerning explainability, interaction, monitoring, and workflow integration.

III. THE AI-DAPT WAY TO MATERIALIZE THE HUMAN OVERSIGHT APPROACHES

A. The AI-DAPT concept and vision

AI-DAPT as a project directly addresses the friction between autonomous efficiency and meaningful human oversight by introducing a data-centric paradigm that fuses end-to-end automation with a HITL approach across the AI-Ops lifecycle [33]. To mitigate the scalability challenges and cognitive fatigue typically associated with continuous human monitoring, the project brings forward a human-AI teaming strategy where machine learning identifies, suggests, and performs complex data operations, allowing human experts to step in as comprehensively informed, final validators during design and execution time of AI pipelines. To prevent the risks of meaningless "rubber stamping" and to avoid the uncontrolled usage of "black-box" models, this oversight is supported by **Explainable AI (XAI) techniques**. This vision is validated in high-stakes settings, including through the project's **healthcare demonstrator** for non-invasive diabetes detection using photoplethysmography. Within this pilot, AI-DAPT deploys synthetic data generation to address low-data scenarios and strict privacy constraints, alongside automated bias detection to actively prevent the amplification of skewed medical recommendations, ultimately empowering healthcare professionals to maintain ethical, accountable, and transparent control over the system without compromising its performance or speed, as they get assisted by the system, but at the same time they also aid the system and control its operation and oversee its outputs.

B. Implementation of Human-Oversight mechanisms in AI-DAPT

In AI-DAPT, human oversight is implemented through a **data-centric adaptive AI-Ops pipeline** in which **human expertise** can be integrated at different stages of the lifecycle, including data preparation, validation, model execution, monitoring, and retraining. A key instrument for this implementation is the **DAVE framework**, which provides a low-code orchestration environment for building and executing AI workflows while integrating external services and validation steps.

DAVE stands for Data Analytics Visualization Environment, a no-code framework that allows the definition of Data or AI pipelines. Leveraging Apache Airflow as the main pipeline orchestrator, scheduler, monitor and executor, DAVE complements it by allowing the creation of these pipelines through block-based programming, instead of the traditional coding approach required by Airflow. Pipelines are defined as Directed Acyclic Graphs (DAGs), a node-and-edge structure where nodes represent computational tasks and

directed edges encode execution dependencies, enforcing a clear start point, end point, and cycle-free execution order. DAVE complements Airflow by leveraging the well established framework while introducing layers of abstraction: operators, as blocks are called in DAVE's environment, are pre-implemented computational units that perform data or AI tasks such as data manipulation like filtering or AI model training, requiring no code authorship; the environment requires no infrastructure configuration; and a built-in converter serializes pipelines into YAML files that are then translated into Airflow DAG structures.

DAVE offers a pipeline creation environment in which the pipeline definition is done by adding blocks via drag-and-drop, providing the necessary operator-specific inputs, and adding connections between operators to create a flow. It also provides all the necessary integration with Airflow, translating the created pipeline into an Airflow-readable format and abstracting the user from all the complexities of data or AI pipeline creation.

The **operators** available in DAVE are divided into three categories. The first are connectors, responsible for handling data loading so that it is available during pipeline execution. The second are transformers, which handle all kinds of data manipulation tasks such as filtering, aggregation, and normalization. The third are analytics operators, which provide a catalog of machine learning algorithms for model training. Together, these three categories represent the core tasks found in any standard data or AI pipeline. Beyond this built-in catalog, AI-DAPT introduced the need to support more complex or specialized tasks that fall outside the scope of DAVE's internal operators. To address this, the concept of external operators was introduced, extending the existing transformer and analytics categories by allowing their functionality to be fulfilled by processes running outside of DAVE's framework.

From a methodological perspective, oversight mechanisms are implemented through external operators, i.e., tasks that interact with external services or tools and are orchestrated within the pipeline through the Airflow-based execution engine. These operators enable the integration of external processes, including services requiring human interaction. The first is the **PythonOperator**, which executes a defined piece of code and marks the task as complete once that execution finishes. The second is the **PythonSensor**, which instead waits for a specific condition or flag to be set by an external process before the task is considered complete. It is worth noting that the PythonOperator and PythonSensor are **native Airflow constructs** and are distinct from the operator abstraction used in DAVE's block-based environment. In the case of **HITL**, external operators leverage the **PythonSensor** to interrupt pipeline execution and place the workflow in a pending state until the required human input is provided through the external service interface. Once the action is completed, the pipeline resumes execution. By contrast, **HOTL** mechanisms rely on the **PythonOperator** configured during the pipeline design phase, where users define parameters, validation rules, or thresholds before execution. During runtime, these operators execute automatically using the predefined configuration, enabling autonomous pipeline operation while preserving human supervision through prior configuration and monitoring conditions. This distinction is illustrated in **Figure 1**, which depicts the execution flow of both operator

types within the pipeline lifecycle. One of the main advantages of this approach lies in the flexibility of these two external operator types, which can be accommodated not only within the three aforementioned categories (connectors, transformers, and analytics), inherently associated with data and AI/ML tasks, but also extended to tasks beyond this scope, such as security-related operations, owing to their versatility and their execution context outside of DAVE itself.

Fig. 1 – Execution lifecycle of HITL (left) and HOTL (right) external operators within a DAVE pipeline. The HITL operator leverages Airflow's PythonSensor to suspend pipeline execution until human input is received; the HOTL operator uses a standard PythonOperator whose behaviour is fully defined at design time, requiring no runtime interaction.

AI-DAPT combines both approaches, HITL for tasks requiring direct expert input, and HOTL for continuous supervision of automated workflows. This hybrid implementation allows human oversight to become a structural element of the pipeline rather than an isolated review step. At a higher level, the framework also supports principles associated with HIC. While not implemented as a specific pipeline operator, human actors retain control over the design and governance of AI workflows, including the selection of operators, configuration of validation mechanisms, and management of model lifecycle processes. Through these mechanisms, human authority is preserved over the operational boundaries and deployment conditions of AI pipelines.

The planned evaluation of this approach is being structured through a set of AI-DAPT demonstrators across multiple domains, including healthcare, robotics, energy, and manufacturing. In each case, AI pipelines are being designed and configured within DAVE using domain-specific datasets and integrating human oversight through the mechanisms described above. The planned analysis will examine how these configurations affect pipeline execution, validation processes, and interaction between human experts and automated components. Among these demonstrators, the healthcare use case is examined in the following section, as it provides a representative scenario for assessing the practical role of human oversight in decision-making environments.

IV. THE AI-DAPT HEALTH CASE

The AI-DAPT health demonstrator provides a representative and high-stakes scenario for analysing the role of human oversight within AI-driven decision-making environments. The use case focuses on non-invasive glucose monitoring through the combination of wearable sensing technologies and machine learning models, aiming to support personalized healthcare while addressing the technical, ethical, and legal challenges associated with the processing of sensitive medical data. Within this context, the demonstrator illustrates how HITL, HOTL, and broader HIC principles can be used in a domain where accuracy, accountability, and trustworthiness are critical.

The system relies on data collected through wearable devices, particularly **photoplethysmography (PPG) signals**, which are combined with clinical reference measurements and additional physiological and contextual data. These data are processed and explored within the AI-DAPT framework to customize AI pipelines, where human oversight is embedded at multiple stages of the lifecycle. In particular, human experts contribute to data validation, model evaluation, and interpretation of outputs, ensuring that the system remains aligned with clinical expectations and domain-specific knowledge. This **integration of expertise** is particularly relevant given the inherent variability of physiological signals, the presence of noise and artefacts in wearable data, and the complexity of correlating indirect measurements with glucose levels.

From a methodological perspective, the health demonstrator adopts a **hybrid oversight approach** that combines HITL and HOTL mechanisms. HITL is primarily applied in stages where expert intervention is necessary, such as data annotation, validation of model outputs, and assessment of clinical relevance. In these cases, pipeline execution may be paused to allow human input, ensuring that critical decisions are informed by medical expertise. At the same time, HOTL mechanisms are employed to supervise automated processes during runtime, where predefined validation rules and monitoring conditions enable continuous oversight without requiring constant human intervention. This combination allows the system to balance efficiency and control, reducing the cognitive burden on experts while preserving their ability to intervene when necessary.

At a higher level, the demonstrator reflects **HIC** principles by maintaining human authority over the design, configuration, and governance of the AI pipelines. Healthcare professionals and researchers define the operational parameters of the system, determine acceptable levels of performance, and retain responsibility for interpreting and acting upon the outputs. This governance layer is particularly important in the medical domain, where the consequences of erroneous predictions can be significant and where accountability must remain clearly attributable to human actors.

The health use case also highlights several **challenges** associated with the implementation of human oversight in AI systems. One of the primary technical challenges relates to data quality and availability. The development of reliable models for non-invasive glucose estimation requires large amounts of high-quality labelled data, which are often difficult to obtain due to privacy constraints, regulatory

requirements, and the complexity of clinical data collection. In this context, the health demonstrator utilizes existing continuous glucose measurement technologies to increase the volume of data collected at a small cost in accuracy. A validation set that is manually collected during clinical visits is also kept aside as the gold standard when it comes to evaluating algorithm performance.

Another key challenge concerns the management of bias and fairness. The demographic composition of clinical datasets may not be fully representative of the broader population, potentially leading to disparities in model performance across different groups. To address this issue, the demonstrator incorporates AI-DAPT's bias detection and monitoring mechanisms, supported by human oversight, to identify and mitigate potential sources of unfairness. This is particularly important in healthcare applications, where unequal performance may have direct implications for patient outcomes.

From an **ethical and legal perspective**, the demonstrator operates under strict data protection and governance requirements, given the processing of sensitive health data. Human oversight plays a central role in ensuring compliance with regulatory frameworks, including the implementation of informed consent procedures, data minimization principles, and secure data handling practices. Moreover, the involvement of human experts contributes to enhancing transparency and trust, particularly when combined with explainable AI techniques that provide insights into model behaviour and decision logic.

Finally, the health demonstrator illustrates the potential **risks associated with human oversight itself**. While the integration of human expertise can improve system reliability and trustworthiness, it may also introduce challenges such as cognitive load, variability in expert judgments, and the risk of over-reliance on automated outputs. These aspects must be carefully managed to avoid phenomena such as automation bias or ineffective oversight. In this regard, the AI-DAPT approach seeks to support meaningful human involvement by providing appropriate tools, interfaces, and explanatory mechanisms that enable experts to effectively understand, evaluate, and control the system.

Overall, the AI-DAPT health case demonstrates how human oversight can be embedded as a structural component of AI pipelines in a complex and sensitive domain. By combining HITL and HOTL mechanisms within a broader HIC governance framework, the demonstrator provides a concrete example of how to balance automation with human control, addressing both the opportunities and the challenges associated with trustworthy AI in healthcare.

V. TECHNICAL, ETHICAL AND LEGAL INSIGHTS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The analysis conducted within the AI-DAPT project provides several initial insights regarding the advantages and challenges of human oversight approaches (HITL, HOTL, and HIC) compared to fully autonomous AI systems. These findings emerge from the conceptual analysis of human oversight mechanisms and the design of the AI-DAPT demonstrators, particularly the health pilot.

A. Technical insights

From a technical perspective, the AI-DAPT approach highlights the **importance of human supervision across the**

lifecycle of AI pipelines, especially in complex data environments such as healthcare.

First, the integration of human expertise within the AI pipeline improves model reliability and robustness. In the health demonstrator, clinicians and technical experts contribute to data validation, interpretation of physiological signals, and review of the data collected and trained model outputs. This equips the system with the ability to detect issues such as model drift, bias, or degraded performance that automated systems may fail to identify.

Second, the project demonstrates the importance of continuous model monitoring and adaptation mechanisms. AI-DAPT pipelines incorporate observability tools that track model performance and trigger alerts when quality thresholds are not met. Human operators can then decide whether to retrain, recalibrate or adjust the model, enabling a controlled adaptive learning process.

Third, preliminary evaluation frameworks defined in the project highlight the need for clear performance metrics to assess AI solutions. In the health use case, metrics such as prediction accuracy (e.g., MAE, R^2 and MARD), percentage of clinically acceptable predictions, and improvements in diagnostic performance have been identified as key indicators to be used in the upcoming evaluation of the system's effectiveness.

B. Ethical and legal insights

From a legal and ethical perspective, the project confirms that human oversight remains a **key requirement for trustworthy AI systems**, particularly in high-risk domains such as healthcare. This conclusion also stems from the emerging AI regulations and frameworks, in particular the **AI Act** (but also the NIST AI Risk Management Framework, for instance), explicitly requiring human oversight for high-risk applications. Humans must be competent, properly trained, and have the authority to override the AI outcomes. According to the **Art. 14** of the AI Act, the AI providers of high-risk systems are required to allow human control or interference with an AI system to achieve effective human oversight. Such AI systems must be designed and developed with appropriate human-machine interface tools and in a way that allow effectively oversight by natural persons during the period in which they are in use, to prevent or minimize the risks to health, safety or fundamental rights. The oversight measures must be proportionate. The requirements stemming from Art. 14 are directly reflected in the technical design of the DAVE framework described in Section IV.B. The human-machine interface tools mandated by the AI Act correspond concretely to DAVE's block-based, low-code pipeline environment, which allows domain experts without software development skills to configure, monitor, and intervene in AI workflows. The oversight mechanisms are structurally embedded in the pipeline through two distinct operator types: the PythonSensor, enforcing a hard stop in execution until explicit human approval is received (implementing HITL), and the PythonOperator, executing predefined validation rules configured by humans prior to runtime (implementing HOTL). This distinction ensures that human oversight is operationally enforced at the pipeline level, in accordance with the proportionality principle of Art. 14.

Following the AI Act's provisions, adequate **XAI techniques** must be adopted, like in AI DAPT, providing transparent reasoning for decisions, including narratives to

improve the effectiveness of explanations and enhancing the interpretability and trustworthiness of ML models, seeking to adopt adequate techniques to communicate complex ML concepts. This is interlinked with the great attention that must be given to the design of adequate user-friendly interfaces, capable of keeping humans engaged and aware, even when not actively involved. This requirement for XAI-supported, user-friendly oversight interfaces is concretely instantiated in the AI-DAPT healthcare demonstrator (Section V). In such a pilot, healthcare professionals interacting with the PPG-based glucose monitoring pipeline have at their disposal, thanks to AI-DAPT, explanations designed to support clinical interpretation, not raw model outputs. The HOTL configuration, relying on PythonOperators, also reduces cognitive load during runtime, as operators do not need to continuously engage with the system. This design choice is ethically significant, since it preserves meaningful oversight whilst limiting the risk of decision fatigue and "rubber-stamping" behaviours identified in Section III as key challenges for human oversight in high-stakes environments.

The AI-DAPT framework incorporates several **governance mechanisms** aimed at ensuring responsible AI deployment. These include ethical impact assessments, compliance with data protection regulations such as the GDPR, and the implementation of informed consent procedures for participants involved in demonstrator activities. These governance mechanisms are technically grounded in the pipeline architecture described in Section IV.B. Data minimisation and access control are enforced through DAVE's connector operators, which handle data loading and limit the scope of data exposed at each pipeline stage. In the healthcare case, bias detection and fairness monitoring (a critical requirement under GDPR and the AI Act for high-risk systems) are implemented through analytics operators integrated in the AI-DAPT health pipeline, as described in Section V. This includes automated detection of demographic disparities in model performance, with alerts that trigger human review through the HITL PythonSensor mechanism. Such a linkage between data governance requirements and concrete pipeline operators shows how ethical compliance is embedded in the technical execution flow rather than addressed as a post-hoc aspect.

Furthermore, the project's focus on hybrid modelling emphasises the human-centric approach to AI development through **science-based approaches**, ensuring that AI systems act as decision-support tools rather than autonomous decision-makers. This approach helps preserve human agency and accountability while reducing the risks associated with automated decision-making. At the same time, they rely on the assumptions that it is essential to understand the differences between the two approaches (HITL and HOTL) and to be able to decide when to opt for one or the other, acknowledging that finding the balance between automation and human judgment is a complex challenge. The choice between HITL and HOTL depends on several factors, such as the complexity of decisions, the context and the stakes involved, and the system maturity. For instance, the HITL is the best choice in case the decisions require context, nuance, or emotional intelligence: the direct human judgment is opportune in case of ethical dilemmas or gray areas. Likewise, the HITL is necessary in critical domain, with higher stakes, such as health and aviation, whilst the HOTL is preferable for routine, high-volume tasks like data entry, as well as for predictable, repeatable tasks. On the other hand,

when an AI system gains reliability, it is possible to move from the HITL to the HOTL. In fact, it is also advisable to continuously evaluate and refine the chosen approach as technology matures. A promising approach is the adaptive human oversight, in which the level of human oversight dynamically adjusts based on the context, the reliability of the system and the risk level.

This principle of adaptive human oversight is reflected in the **technical architecture of DAVE**. The distinction between the PythonSensor (HITL) and PythonOperator (HOTL) is a configurable parameter that pipeline designers can adjust based on the sensitiveness and criticality of each task. In the healthcare pilot, for example, data annotation and model output validation for glucose estimation (tasks requiring clinical nuance) are implemented as HITL steps, that pause execution pending expert's input. By contrast, routine signal quality checks and bias monitoring (tasks with well-defined thresholds) are implemented as HOTL steps, running autonomously but log results for asynchronous human review. The performance metrics used to assess these processes (such as MAE, R^2 , MARD) might also provide the empirical basis for deciding when a pipeline stage has matured sufficiently to shift from HITL to HOTL supervision, thereby grounding the governance decision in measurable technical evidence.

On the other hand, the choice between these two approaches must also consider the interpretation of the **Art. 22 of the GDPR** [34], establishing that the data subject has the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects concerning him or her or similarly significantly affects him or her (such as credit rejections or automated hiring decisions). Individuals have the right to human intervention.

Article 22 provisions can't be avoided by fabricating human involvement [35]: to qualify as human involvement, the oversight of the decision must be meaningful, rather than just a token gesture. The need of meaningful human oversight also applies to AI systems: it is important to consider the concrete frameworks in which humans interact with automated decisions, what kind of decision options they have, if and to what extent they have sufficient data available to inform their decision, the time allocated for their input/oversight and other factors. Only in this way it is possible to proceed with the responsible development of automated systems, designing human-machine relationships that align with societal values and priorities, going beyond merely implementing technical safeguards, to implement effective human oversight, giving rise to collaborative frameworks where humans and AI systems complement each other's. The intricate nature of collaboration, however, is challenging and the integration of human expertise and judgment into the ML process adds complexity to the learning process, also considering the uncertainties of the delineation of the collaboration mode and of the amalgamation of machine and human outputs across parallel and sequential contexts.

In addition, it is paramount to safeguard the data labelers' and experts' comfort and wellbeing, including fair wages, safe conditions, and psychological support such experts, who engage in tedious or distressing content review.

Considering the possible cognitive overload, alternatives are currently under exploration, including the adoption of automated quality control mechanisms for identifying and correcting inconsistencies or errors in the training data, either flagging questionable labels for human review or automatically correcting obvious errors. Thanks to the continuous training and capability of the AI systems to learn and improve over time as more data becomes available, the initial phase when humans provide initial labels can be followed by the second phase, when the system can retrain and adjust its model as it receives new data. This approach would also contribute to address the issue of scalability

Going further, with the emergence of **Agentic AI and Multi-Agent Systems (MAS)**, which are becoming increasingly sophisticated and deployed across critical domains and present unique ethical complexities, the need for robust ethical frameworks and for an alignment of the human oversight paradigm is stringent. The trends are moving towards, on the one hand, embedding ethical reasoning directly into agent architectures, including value alignment modules, decision transparency mechanisms and harm prevention capabilities to navigate complex trade-offs whilst maintaining core principles, and, on the other hand, in addressing the ethical challenges arising from interactions between agents and from collective behaviour in case of MAS. On top of this framework the human oversight might be ensured in the form of HOTL, providing feedback and supervision of deployment and operation.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

The emergence and consolidation of the human oversight approach – in its dual models HITL and HOTL- for maintaining human agency and accountability in the algorithmic-driven decision-making processes offer great promise in several domains to manage risks, solve problems, ensure compliance and address ethical concerns, with the anticipated potential for improved performance, accuracy, users' satisfaction and trust building pending demonstrator based evaluation, moving steps ahead for the deployment and use of ethically-driven and trustworthy AI-empowered solutions. In order to ensure effective human machine collaboration, such a human input should be meaningful, not a simplistic "human approval". This requires adopting a human-centric approach, functional to avoid the cognitive overload of the experts, focusing on human oversight, especially HOTL models, for critical aspects, whilst exploring the adoption of automated quality control mechanisms for the other aspects, as well as partially relying on the continuous training and capability of the AI systems itself to learn and improve over time, thereby also contributing to address the issue of scalability. From a technical standpoint, the practical implementation of these oversight mechanisms requires orchestration frameworks capable of embedding human interaction directly into pipeline execution flows, rather than treating it as an external review step. The experience drawn from DAVE demonstrates that a low-code, operator-based architecture, where HITL and HOTL behaviours are defined as native pipeline building blocks on top of a workflow engine such as Airflow, offers a viable and scalable path towards operationalising human oversight, without requiring domain experts to engage in software development tasks to configure or deploy these mechanisms. In the same direction, the emergence of Agentic AI and Multi-Agent Systems (MAS) also demands for an

alignment of the human oversight paradigm, where, moving towards the embedding of the ethical reasoning directly into agent architectures, such a human oversight is expected to increasingly take the form of HOTL, providing feedback and supervision of deployment and operation.

A multi-disciplinary approach, combining the legal and ethical perspective with the technological breakthroughs and intersecting computer science, cognitive science, and psychology, is highly recommended to address the challenges raised by the human involvement in the AI-empowered decision-making.

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